

Progress towards Federated Logistics through the Integration of TEN-T into A Global Trade Network

D6.5 Innovation Management Report and patent Filings procedures

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Glossary of terms and abbreviations used

Abbreviation / Term	Description
AB	Advisory Board
AI	Artificial Intelligence
ALICE	Alliance for Logistics Innovation through Collaboration in Europe

AM	Administrative Manager
API	Application Programming Interface
B2B	Business-to-Business
B2C	Business-to-Consumer
CA	Consortium Agreement
CEN/TS	European Committee for Standardisation / Technical Specification
DMP	Data Management Plan
EC	European Commission
EGTN	EU-Global T&L Network
ETA	Estimated Time of Arrival
EU	European Union
EU PO	European Patent Office
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable (referring to data management)
GA	Grant Agreement
GCC	GNU Compiler Collection
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GSIN	Global Shipment Identification Number
GTIN	Global Trade Item Number
H2020	Horizon 2020 – Framework Program 8
IBM	IBM Ireland Innovation Exchange Team
ICT	Information & Communications Technology
IDT	Invention Development Team
IM	Innovation Manager
Industry 4.0	Industry 4.0 is commonly referred to as the fourth industrial revolution
IoT	Internet of Things
IP/IPR	Intellectual Property/ Intellectual Property Rights
IPSE	IoT Privacy and Security Engine
ISO	International Standardisation Institute
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LL(s)	Living Lab(s)

PI	Physical Internet
PM	Project Manager
PMB	The Project Management Board
PO	Project Officer
PoC	Proof of Concept
PSS	Privacy Security and Safety
SC	Supply Chain
SDLC	Software Development Life Cycle
T&L	Transport and Logistics
TCP/IP	Transmission Control Protocol/Internet Protocol
TENT-T	Trans-European Transport Network
UC	Use Case
UNCTAD	United Nations Conference on Trade and Development
WP	Work Package

1 Executive Summary

PLANET project aims to advance European Commission strategy for Smart, Green and Integrated Transport and Logistics (EGTN), by efficiently interconnecting TEN-T and Rail-Freight Corridors with geopolitical developments (e.g., future New Silk Road) and optimising the use of current & emerging transport modes. To achieve these goals PLANET project, utilizes cutting-edge technologies such as IoT, Blockchain, Artificial Intelligence etc., hand in hand with innovative Transport & Logistics theories and practices such as Physical Internet, Sycromodality and others for offering new services to T&L actors. These services aim to assist T&L actors in improving business processes and achieve better business outcomes through accomplishing reductions in compliance, operational and administrative costs, more transparent and efficient freight management, improved customer experience/satisfaction as well as present the merits of increasing the collaboration and coordination among the different T&L actors.

The main objective of PLANET's WP6 was to set up and implement all the necessary processes for the realization of PLANET objectives and deliverables, including the Innovation Management and the submission of three innovative patents at the EU and/or US patent offices, under a unanimous agreement from PLANET's consortium. For this reason, a detailed framework for selecting and prioritizing three highly strategic and commercially valued project's outputs is reported. This includes a framework of pre-designed criteria for scoring all prospect patents that weight three focus areas a) their alignment with EC and project objectives b) satisfying patenting fundamentals criteria and c) alignment on business value and giving the project's partners a valuable asset and a competitive advantage.

In addition, PLANET's Innovation Management except for safeguarding patent filling submission, had a specific focus on identifying the most innovative outputs and ideas generated during PLANET project and to foster their further evolution. To this end PLANET's Innovation Management utilized project's Innovation Registry questionnaire, periodically updated throughout project lifetime, for pinpointing the most promising and innovative outputs, as well as facilitate their further evolution though PLANET's Innovation and Commercialization Board feedback. Finally, through this process and cross-consortium interactions, a list of 11 novel ideas or services were identified, and their key characteristics are outlined in this report.

Finally, the report describes the actions for completing the EU and US legally compliant formal patent applications for the selected three patents which focuses on the areas of multi-modal documentation management for dynamic optimization at logistic hubs, route selection for Physical Internet (PI) freight orchestration and Physical Internet (PI) dynamic port selection.

2 Introduction

This report has been prepared in the context of WP6-Project management and, more specifically, in respect of Task 6.3 -Innovation and Data Management within PLANET, which includes the Innovation Management report deliverable. The report focusses on describing the innovation management methodologies and their key characteristics that PLANET’s utilizes for creating and implementing a versatile and effective framework able to accommodate project needs. In addition, the report includes key statistics, summaries of reports and information’s about EC agenda, used during project lifetime for highlighting the importance of Innovation Management and the patent benefits as well as for motivating consortium partners about them.

Furthermore, D6.5 Innovation Management and Patent Filing report, except for summarizing the underlying principles, methodology, and activities that were vital in creating this report, also set forth the selected 3 patents that are a direct outcome of PLANET’s consortium work and project innovative vision. More specifically, the first invention relates to the technical field of digitalization and decentralization of multi-modal logistics documentation, where digital and trustworthy availability of shipments documentation is key to enable real-time multimodal routing and capacity optimization. The second invention is a recursive and multi-criteria physical internet freight orchestration process aiming to overcome technical deficiencies of the static freight forwarder routing selection. The last patent relates to the technical field of physical internet (PI) and more particularly to (PIN) port selection for PI enabled routing aiming to address deficiencies in respect to maritime port selection in supply chain logistics.

Finally, it should be noted that PLANET’s Innovation Management Methodology activities central focus was the identification and prioritization of PLANET’s strategic and commercially sensitive intellectual property through patent filings. The subsequent enablement of commercialisation of the innovations and market analysis will take place and D5.6 Business & Commercialisation plan report.

2.1 Mapping PLANET Outputs

The purpose of this section is to map PLANET’s Grant Agreement commitments, both within the formal Deliverable and Task description, against the project’s respective outputs and work performed. The table below fulfills that goal and serves as a guide, with the first column containing the deliverable and associated tasks or subtasks as described in the Grant Agreement while the second column indicates where in this report this topic is discussed, and the third column gives a brief executive summary.

Table 1: Adherence to PLANET’s GA Deliverable & Tasks Descriptions

PLANET GA Component Title	PLANET GA Component Outline	Respect ive Docum ent Chapter (s)	Justification
DELIVERABLE			

<p>D6.5 Innovation managemen t report and Patent Filings</p>	<p>Innovation management report</p>	<p>Chapter 3,4</p>	<p>Chapter 3 explains the methodologies and concepts that PLANET’s Innovation Management utilizes. In addition, it describes PANET’s Innovation Registry and the most important activities and milestones in project methodology for promoting an innovation culture and engaging consortium members regarding IP.</p> <p>Chapter 4 describes outlines the identified 11 innovative outcomes, their key characteristics and PLANET’s ICB feedback about them</p>
	<p>Patent Filings & Patent Office docket numbers evidencing “Patent Pending”.</p>	<p>Chapter 3,4,5</p>	<p>Section 3.5 describes the timeline of actions for engaging, discussing and coordinating actions regarding patent filing procedures.</p> <p>Chapter 4 describe the various characteristics that a patent must fulfil, PLANET’s patent filing strategies and patent selection procedures.</p> <p>Chapter 5 describes in detail the 3 selected Patents, search report, their patent filing status as well as business and commercial value.</p>
<p>TASKS</p>			
<p>T6.3 Innovation and Data Managemen t</p>	<p>The objective of this task is to set up an innovation management process as specified in section 2.4 and to manage the preparation and submission of patent filings.</p>	<p>Chapter 3.1 Chapter 3.2 Chapter 4.1 Chapter 4.4 Chapter 4.5</p>	<p>Chapter 3.1 and 3.2 describe the Innovation Methodologies and Concepts utilized in the project</p> <p>Chapter 3.6 introduces the principles, goals and actions for creating PLANET’s Innovation Registry.</p> <p>Chapter 4.1 presents the most innovative ideas pinpointed by PLANET’s Innovation Registry Questionnaire.</p> <p>Chapter 4.4 describes PLANET’s patents selection criteria and</p>

			<p>Chapters 4.5 describe PLANET’s patentability strategy.</p>
<p>ST6.3.3 PLANET IP Protection</p>	<p>PLANET’s IP Protection addresses management of the main IPR activities of the project and, specifically, focuses on the central assets that will be required for the project’s successful implementation and commercial exploitation of the expected results.</p> <p>All IP produced will be systematically monitored along with the potential IPR attached to them (e.g. copyright, inventive steps, patent art), as well as verified and approved for the successful execution of the project with a strong bias/prioritisation towards incentivising and underwriting successful commercial outcomes.</p> <p>PLANET intends to file at least 3 patents from the project, prioritising the commercially sensitive and strategic innovation. PLANET will also conduct a global search against the prior art for potential inventions, trademarks and other IPRs where necessary and will evaluate the costs for IPR protection, subsequently confirming the appropriate filing regions prior to filing formal patent documents.</p> <p>It is anticipated that PLANET’s IP filing strategy will prioritise the project’s partners in a successful commercial trajectory. A cautious monitoring of the project from the IPR point of view will ensure that CDA, NDA and IPR for all partners (foreground and background) are fully respected.</p>	<p>Chapter 5</p>	<p>Chapter 5.1 include the patent filled with docket number 6200-037BE for Digitalization and decentralization of multi-modal logistics documentation. In addition, the chapter includes a detailed description and illustration of the inventions as well as the respective, prior to submission, novelty report and business value for the assignee.</p> <p>Chapter 5.2 describes the patent filled with docket number 6200-038U for a method for recursive multi-criteria physical Internet (PI) freight orchestration. In addition, the chapter includes a detailed description and illustration of the inventions as well as it’s search report and business value for the assignee.</p> <p>Chapter 5.3 presents the patent Application 6200-039U for physical internet dynamic principal interface node (PIN) port selection, accompanied by throughout description of and illustration of the inventions as well as the respective, prior to submission, novelty report and business value for the assignee.</p>

2.2 Deliverable Overview and Report Structure

This deliverable includes the methodological background as well as the activities implemented during PLANET lifetime, for engaging consortium members and facilitating the developments of innovations of the project, with the utter goal of filling 3 patents of high strategic importance at European and US patent offices. In more detail, this deliverable consists of 5 chapters, structured as follows:

Chapter 1: Contains the executive summary of the D6.5 Innovation management report and Patent Filings

Chapter 2: Describe the structure and the content of the current deliverable, as well as map the work and activities undertaken with PLANET's Grant Agreement respective tasks and deliverable.

Chapter 3: This chapter describes PLANET's Innovation Management methodology and overall scope. In detail, it explains the various Innovation Management methodologies utilized for identifying and managing project innovative outputs, the content and goals of PLANET's Innovation Registry and Questionnaire, as well as the most important milestones in the patent filing process.

Chapter 4: This chapter describes PLANET's Innovation Registry items and their key elements. In addition, it describes the processes for assessing and selecting the 3 candidate patents for filings. Finally, it includes the associated KPI driven framework, ensuring that our work and efforts pay attention to a broad class of innovation KPIs. Finally, this chapter outlines the different patent filings options and strategies that were available, and subsequently justifies the preferred regional patent filing strategy.

Chapter 5: This chapter provides a detailed description of PLANET innovations that were prioritized for patent filings, along with their novelty study conducted prior to patents docket's submissions. Furthermore, for each patent the background of the invention and the related art is presented, accompanied by a detailed description of the process each invention implements, their architecture and their potential business benefits for their owners.

3 PLANET Innovation Management

PLANET's Innovation Management primary focus was the identification and protection of project's and consortium partners intellectual property and outputs. Innovation management in PLANET includes the implementation of all necessary steps and actions needed to understand, link, evaluate and prioritise projects outputs, with the goal being to attest for filling and finally patenting three project's outputs of high commercial and strategic value. Finally, PLANET Innovation Management aside from realizing the goal of filling 3 patents, also provides the necessary evidence for the formal filing docket numbers, as well as creating a framework for a consortium consensus regarding the selected 3 patents.

PLANET project management and governance framework were established to ensure the reliable control and monitoring of PLANET activities and outputs. This framework as well as its respective processes and procedures made it possible for the project to attain its technological/business/institutional objectives, as well as substantiate a structured framework for making project-wide decisions. According to Project Management structure, the Innovation Management methodology is executed under the instructions of the project's coordinator (INLE) with the assistance of PLANET consortium. In this way, PLANET's Innovation Management was able to lead to efficient coordination and collaboration between all involved parties and create an environment for galvanizing and incubating innovative ideas, along with embedding measures for continuous communications within project's inner and external environments.

FIGURE 15: PLANET Management Structure

Figure 1 PLANET Management Structure

In addition, the Innovation Manager role was to support PLANET partners' work and assists them to evolve their work into commercially exploitable products/assets as well as offer advice and guidance to consortium members regarding the best international practices on innovation management. Finally, PLANET's Innovation & Commercialisation Board (ICB)² had a key role to project's innovation management approach, by providing further feedback and guidance to PLANET's consortium members regarding their innovative outputs. PLANET's ICB consist of prominent and highly experienced researchers and industry experts from various domains (Transport & Logistics, Software Development, ITC), who already have successfully managed the challenging and complex work of filing successful patents in their professional careers and bring early-stage R&D to market.

² Innovation & Commercialisation Board (ICB): The ICB, chaired by INLE, includes BlockLab, UIRR, PAN, HARDT, FV, PP, COSTech, JD and PNO.

Concluding, this section offered a summary of the principles that PLANET Innovation Methodology adheres to while in the following sections presents the framework of PLANET Innovation Management procedures and stakeholders engagement activities.

3.1 PLANET state of the art Innovation Management Methodologies

For creating and implementing a versatile and effective Innovation Management methodology able to accommodate PLANET project needs several innovation management theories and tools were utilized. More specifically, these tools help us customize our methods as follows:

- The **S-Curve Framework**³ is a methodology typically used to substantiate the origin and progress of disruptive and/or radical innovations and for planning new technology development. Of significant importance to PLANET is factoring in the weighting of technology maturity into PLANET's innovation management methodology and KPI assessment framework.
- **Oslo Manual**^{4,5} is one of the foremost international sources of guidelines for the collection and use of data on innovation activities in the industry. Initially published in October 2005 (Oslo Manual 3rd edition) and with a new release of the revised Oslo Manual in 2018⁶. The third edition the third edition was updated taking into consideration the insights gain from innovation surveys in OECD member and non-member countries, which investigated the field of non-technological innovation as well as the linkages between different innovation types and their economic impact's. The fourth and more recent version focuses on methods for designing, using and analyzing innovation indicators. In the context of PLANET Innovation Management is going to leverage best practices within these manual that are associated with assessing the potential economic impact of innovation and, consequently, this will be reflected in our methodological assessment framework of project's outputs.
- The Stage Gate model⁷ is among the most used industry standards for supporting and managing new product innovations. This model implements wide processes that incorporate performance-driven practices into concrete steps. In this way, the State Gate model enables the engagement of actors at various decision-making levels, supporting quality-driven execution principles and associated decisions, thus allowing products to reach markets quicker and in support of economic ROIs. Elements of particular interest for PLANET innovation management methodology, which aims at embedding them in order to prioritise its economic and strategic imperatives.
- The Funnel model⁸ considers the innovation process beginning with a wide variety of inputs and systematically refines and prioritises these by developing a shorter list of priority goals that can be completed and introduced to the market too, following specific design stages such as idea generation, development objectives, project planning and management, task execution, continuous learning and post-project enhancements and optimization. PLANET will certainly be required to make decisions and prioritize actions or outputs and therefore will pay specific attention to soliciting,

³ Foster, R. N. (1986). *Innovation, the attacker's advantage*. New York: Summit.

⁴ OECD. (2002). *Frascati Manual: Proposed Standard Practice for Surveys on Research and Experimental Development* (6th ed.). OECD.

⁵ OECD. (2005). *Oslo Manual: proposed guidelines for collecting and interpreting technological innovation data* (3rd ed.). Paris: OECD Publishing.

⁶ OECD/Eurostat (2018), *Oslo Manual 2018: Guidelines for Collecting, Reporting and Using Data on Innovation, 4th Edition*, The Measurement of Scientific, Technological and Innovation Activities, OECD Publishing, Paris/Eurostat, Luxembourg, <https://doi.org/10.1787/9789264304604-en>.

⁷ Cooper, R. G. (1990). Stage-Gate Systems - a New Tool for Managing New Products. *Business Horizons*, 33(3), 44-54.

⁸ Wheelright, S. C., & Clark, K. B. (1992). *Revolutionizing product development*. New York: The Free Press.

prioritising and hierarchizing ideas in the spirit of an open as well as joint procedure that the Funnell model advocates.

- The top best practices from Monnier's Advancement Matrix⁹, which is a tool focused on determining the level of innovation for an organization as well as embracing a method for gauging innovations at 7 levels, which can easily be applied to most industrial applications. This methodology is made up of a two-dimensional matrix representing both the market level/opportunity relative to the new idea. Elements of this matrix will be used in PLANET, to evaluate the technical degree of project innovation and/or the importance of a new output, either product or service, or solution based upon the innovation. Finally, this tool will evaluate innovative ideas/output relevance to reviewing the innovation's ability of the major outputs of the project in respect of e.g. patent filing choice.
- The European Commission Innovation Radar^{10 11 12} is an initiative from the European Commission focused on the identification of high potential innovations in EC funded projects and help innovators by steering different actions and facilitating them to reach their potential capacity. Elements of the EC's Innovation Radar will be integrated in PLANET's Innovation management including: analyzing the maturity of innovations from the project, prioritising promising innovators and innovations from the point of view of transforming their outputs into commercial exploitable assets; providing support and expertise in regard to relevant steps to gain access to the market; supporting innovators through entrepreneurship activities such as collaboration, networking, etc..

Concluding, the role and goals of PLANET's Innovation Management and methodologies mentioned is providing guidance to the consortium partners about best international practices as described above for identifying and fostering innovation enablers/driving factors, supporting the innovation management processes as well as identifying, scoring and filling three innovative patents relevant to project's impact points and aspirations.

⁹ B. Monnier "Management of Innovation in Research", *Advanced Materials Research*, Vols. 452-453, pp. 491-495, 2012

¹⁰ Van Roy, Vincent, and Daniel Nepelski. Validation of the Innovation Radar assessment framework. No. JRC110926. Joint Research Centre (Seville site), 2018.

¹¹ Nepelski, Daniel, and Giuseppe Piroli. "Organizational diversity and innovation potential of EU-funded research projects." *The Journal of Technology Transfer* 43.3 (2018): 615-639.

¹² González, Jaqueline Vargas, et al. "Critical Success Factors (CSF) to Commercializing Technologies in Universities: The Radar Framework." *International Conference on Electronic Government and the Information Systems Perspective*. Springer, Cham, 2018.

3.2 PLANET Innovation Management Best Practices in CEN/TS 16555-01

The Innovation Management (IM) methodology applied in PLANET acknowledges the important distinction between Invention and Innovation, with the invention encompassing the creation of a novel idea or concept, while innovation including all the necessary acts of turning the novel concepts into successful commercial and/or economic outputs¹³. In context, PLANET IM methodological framework leverages several best practices in peer review¹⁴, utilize the CEN/TS 16555-01 family of standards and pays special attention to guidance (and key innovation questions) as depicted by Finn Kollerup in the figure below, and is broadly in line with the innovation process flow that is similar to that illustrated at the left hand side of figure below, by Popescu et al¹⁵, at the left hand side of the figure below.

Figure 2¹⁶ Key Elements Covered in CEN/TS 16555-1

CEN/TS 16555 framework, originally published quite recently in 2013, which emanates from the European Committee for Standardization (CEN) after negotiations between 32 Member States. CEN/TS 16555 was designed to bolster innovation in organizations irrespective of their national origin, type, size, or industry and aimed to establish a new international standard for innovation management with a global reach. This Technical Specification (Innovation management Part 1: Innovation management system, CEN/TS 16555-1:2013) assisting guide actors in the development of an innovation strategy and vision, building an ethos and culture to promote innovation, exploiting a best-fit innovation process, leveraging methods, techniques, and tools to manage innovation and gauging innovation results. These elements are taken as input and used as a basis to guide and design our innovation management methodology. Of course, of paramount importance are those questions that are relevant to educating, fathoming, creating confidence, and substantiating the potential innovation under a commercially oriented environment, as stipulated in PLANET goals which, among others, is to prioritise patent

¹³ <http://www.hksq.org/HKSTP-HKSQ-InnoMS-Seminar-20150124-Lotto.pdf>

¹⁴ Barandika, Gotzone, et al. "Design of the Procedure Attached to the Process "Innovation Management" of Eidos, a Materials Science Research Group, and Analysis of its Influence on the Formation of Doctorates." Conference proceedings. The future of education. libreriauniversitaria. it Edizioni, 2014.

¹⁵ Popescu, Maria, and Lidia Mândru. "Relationship between Quality Planning and Innovation." Bulletin of the Transilvania University of Braşov, Series V, Economic Sciences 9.58 (2016): 203-212

¹⁶ <https://finnkollerup.com/2015/09/20/use-the-european-innovation-management-standard-as-your-innovation-checklist>, Sept 10, 2018

filing process in support keeping a commercial trajectory by taking into consideration the special interest of PLANET's consortium members.

Finally, PLANET's innovation management activities can incorporate conventional software development SDLC Phases as depicted by Specht¹⁷ and closely aligned with the R&D phases and development and deployment of project's technical outputs according to project's plans timeline, while ensuring that the scientific and technical innovations of PLANET project have been obtained upon high quality criteria. Likewise, the work being performed in WP6 provides support and guidance to scientific, software or technical outputs and expertise at their respective lifecycles, so as to help ensure the achievement of PLANET's beyond of the state-of-the-art objectives.

Figure 3 Innovation Management Process in a Generalized SDLC

3.3 PLANET Innovation Management Framework and Intellectual Property Protection

PLANET's Innovation Management approach included patent protection for project outputs in areas of relevant interest, eventually enabling the exploitation of the innovative outputs of the consortium as well as its commercialized actors, unhindered by competitors beyond Europe. By formal protection at EUIPO and USPTO, a patent will certainly stand for a property right to the owner of the patent, stipulated in a detailed file consisting of dozens of pages of background, context, specification, diagrams, and patent claims. This property right conferred is "exclusionary" and deprives others from making, using, offering for sale, or importing a product that practices the invention (the term of a Patent's protection is usually twenty years from earliest filing day). In addition, securing PLANET's commercial and strategic innovation assists the European Commission in keeping business and financial benefits as well as associated possibilities within Europe, whilst supporting EU's reputation on a global scale for innovation and research excellence. Finally, our work will incorporate the following three objectives:

¹⁷ Specht, G. (2002). F&E Management: Kompetenz im Innovationsmanagement. Stuttgart: Schaffer Poeschel.

- i. Circling the strategic and/or commercially sensitive innovation, with the goal to protect this “in Europe” and “for Europe”, paying attention to open sourcing as much as we can outside this for others to use/build-on/build-from.
- ii. Ideally, prioritising the patent activities towards giving IP-filing advantages to SMEs in the consortium - and helping to underpin business roadmaps and commercial trajectories (i.e. in support of economic KPIs)
- iii. Collaboratively enumerating, scoring, and prioritising the places where we will focus PLANETS’ IP related actions – ideally prioritising efforts that have a planned commercial trajectory and/or strategic interest to PLANET’s industry partners (i.e. collaborative team decision, where all partners have a vote/say and collectively decide together).

3.4 Patentability Requirements

In order for an idea, process, output (product or service) to be able to be patented, it must fulfil the following 3 characteristics, which are novelty, non-obviousness and utility. Therefore, PLANET’s candidate patents must satisfy these criteria:

- Novelty - A machine, manufacture, process, or composition of matter must be new or in other words, not have been previously described or known. In terms of what constitutes prior and/or background art, the legal definition is anything out there in the world that can be found and inferred as reasonably similar or identical.
- Non-Obviousness - The difference must be sufficient to what is already out there, such that the invention is not obvious to the industry/manufacturer/firm, the inventions aim to be patented, i.e. sufficiently different from what has been used or described before and non-obvious to a person having ordinary skill in the area of technology.
- Utility - The invention must have a practical and applicable use and purpose as well as satisfying them, by being capable of producing the intended results.

Keeping in mind the aforementioned principles, PLANET Innovation Management efforts aim to ensure that patentable innovations will be a) Inventions that are of a “patentable subject”, b) Inventions are “new or novel” (not done before), c) Inventions are “Useful” and have reasonably substantial & credible use, d) Invention are “Operative” & performs intended purpose, e) Invention are “Non-obvious” - i.e. must not be apparent to one of ordinary skill in the relevant art, and f) Inventions are “Implementable” – i.e. sufficient detail provided to show implementation is possible. In addition, specific focus will be given into identifying what is the current state of the art in order to distinguish what is and what is “not” Patentable, including:

- Laws of nature, physical phenomena and abstract ideas
- A mere idea or suggestion
- A discovery, scientific theory or mathematical method
- An aesthetic creation
- A scheme, rule or method for performing a mental act, playing a game or doing business, or a computer program
- A presentation of information

- A procedure for surgical or therapeutic treatment, or diagnosis, to be practiced on humans or animals
- In Europe, business method patents are not Patentable (unlike the USA)

Finally, PLANET's IM also takes into account the business value in the areas/industries the patent belongs, by through the following criteria:

- Potential licensing value - e.g. are others likely to practice the invention
- Defensive value – e.g. are others likely to have similar inventions in their portfolio
- Ease of detectability - Can we tell when someone else practices the invention (the harder it is to detect/decide, the lower the potential licensing and/or business value)
- Degree of interest to current or future competitors
- Potential market coverage & likely significance relative to Customers
- Strategic importance to the Commission (i.e. directly relevant to PLANET ambitions)

3.5 Innovation Management activities towards IP: stakeholders' engagement

The table below summarises the most important milestones during PLANET lifetime for informing and engaging PLANET's partners about PLANET's innovation management methodology and patent filings procedures. More specifically, in this section the Patent Training Session and Schedule patent adjudication meetings are discussed in detail, while Innovation Registry Questionnaire and Patent Selection results are extensively described in the following chapters.

Inlecom provided a comprehensive training session regarding PLANET Innovation Management and Patent Filing methodology as well as the timeline of actions to the consortium on June 17th, 2021, during WP1, WP2 & Innovation Management workshop. This training session began with the potential benefits of IP protection presented extensively to the consortium, followed by a legal and technical discussion of what constitutes a patent and patentable IP, the nature and type of viable patents, as well as the types of patents succeeding today. This training continued with a summary of EU and US PO Guidelines on patentability, with details regarding prerequisites for creating a patent and the specific attributes of the invention. At the end of the session, a series of innovation KPIs and related rationale was presented including focus areas, innovation KPIs, rationale/explanation and scoring. Consortium commercial aspirations were also discussed as reflected in the GA, with the contractual agreement for 3 patents in the project timeline.

In addition, during the training session, another key point of discussion was public and/or external disclosure. External disclosure of key concepts and/or inventive steps constitutes external divulgence, e.g., external presentations, publications, conferences, website postings, discussions with outside parties, such disclosure would ultimately invalidate the potential for patent filings under both EU and US patent law. Consequently, it was discussed and agreed as important that inventive concepts are kept internal to the consortium until such time that confirmation of patent office filings are affirmed. Likewise, it was agreed that it is acceptable to discuss progress & detail with the EU Commission, so long as we ask for confidentiality if discussing areas in scope for patent filings. Furthermore, it was agreed that the Innovation Manager will guide the consortium in terms of reviewing material, papers, publications, presentations prior to external disclosure if needed, with the general advice to check first if one is unsure, as it is in the consortium's best interests to keep the strongest patent ideas "internal" to the consortium until EU and US Patent Office Patent filings are confirmed. Finally, PLANET's Innovation Registry goals and Innovation Registry Questionnaire were described in detail, including the underlying logic and goals of each question as well as presenting indicative answers and examples for guiding on

answering PLANET's Innovation registry questionnaire. Last but not least, another aim of PLANET'S Innovation Registry was to effectively motivate PLANET partners from an early stage to articulate and bring forth their innovative work and ideas.

Table 2 Milestones in Deliverables Preparation Timeline or Stakeholders Engagement Timeline and Actions

Step	Action	(Planned) Timeline	Goals
1	Overview of Patent Process and Goal	PLANET 1 st GA	Engage partners and make them aware of what, where, when about patenting processes
2	Quote and select patent attorney	End of Year 1 of the project	Achieve a consensus about attorney selection
3	Deep-dive patent training session	Shortly After year 1 of the project	Engage and motivate partners about the characteristics and the benefits of patents
4	Innovation questionnaire v1	Mid-year 1 of the project	Facilitate the detection of innovative and patentable ideas at the early stage of the project
5	Schedule patent adjudication meeting with relevant partners	Mid-year 1 of the project	Selecting and filing the candidate patents by end of year 2, (which allows time in the project for prosecution and granting patent)
6	Patent Selection	Before the end of year 2	Prioritize the 3 most innovative and commercial patents
7	Engage attorney to file selected/prioritized patents	Around the end of year 2	Achieving Project goal of producing 3 Innovative Patents

3.6 PLANET Innovation Registry Scope and Goals

Innovation Registry was introduced to PLANET project for capturing PLANET partner's innovative work and their various innovative ideas during PLANET lifetime. To achieve this goal, a tailor-made questionnaire was created leveraging the different innovation management methodologies and best practices described in the previous sections above. The Innovation Registry questionnaire consisted of 12 questions, a mix of open and multiple-choice questions, focusing on capturing consortium members innovative outputs and their linkages to PLANET vision, the added value to their operations and for external stakeholders or the industry as well as investigating possible barriers to their future development and future evolution plans. Also, it should be noted that this questionnaire was distributed electronically to consortium partners through European Commission EU Survey tool¹⁸ where all the data are stored on the servers of the European Commission's Data Centre and it's privacy and security terms are compliant with GDPR and project's rules. Finally, PLANET partners' answers were provided

¹⁸ <https://www.gasncfunc.eu/eusurvey/home/about>

to PLANET Innovation and Commercialisation Board for recommendations as well as for a preliminary assessment of their innovative dimension, corroborating the patenting filling processes, based on the following criteria:

- **Utility:** The idea/output must have practical and applicable use/purpose as well by being capable of producing (the intended) results
- **Novelty:** the idea/output it essentially introduces something new, something that hasn't been done before, or something that it does not form as part of the state of the art
- **Non-Obviousness:** the idea/output must not be apparent/obvious to anyone in the same area or industry/manufacturer/firm or anyone of ordinary skill.

Table 3 PLANET's Innovation Registry Questionnaire

Question Title	Type of Question	Question's Instructions
Key Needs/Objectives & relevance to PLANET UCs	Open question	What is the primary business/technical/authority imperatives the relevant project innovation(s) are trying to address? How do those needs/objectives relate to one or more project Use Cases?
Innovation Type	Multiple choice question	- New/ Significantly improved product ¹⁹ - New/ Significantly improved service ²⁰ (except consulting ones) - New / Significantly improved process ²¹ - New/ Significantly improved marketing method - New/ Significantly improved Organisational method - Consulting services
Project Innovation Description	Open question	Please describe the relevant innovative idea/outcome in detail.
Innovation Justification	Open question	Why do you consider those ideas as innovative and/or beyond the current state of the art?
Innovation Readiness	Open question	Please indicate if your innovation(s) is a) under development, b) already developed but not yet exploited c) already being exploited. If possible, indicate project start and project end expected TRL level
Internal Value	Open question	What is the added value the innovation(s) introduces to your current mode of Operations?
External Value	Open question	External Value: Please explain the broader benefits of your innovation(s).

¹⁹ Product refers to a new good which is usually a tangible object.

²⁰ Service Output is a new service is usually intangible, such as insurance

²¹ Process Output is a new or significantly improved production or delivery method..

		E.g., benefits for the Society/ Industry/ Scientific/Research/ Environment/Broader
Barriers	Open question	Please identify and describe potential barriers to adoption, usage, and/or market entry for your innovation(s) E.g. in the areas of IPR, Standards, Regulation, Financing, Workforce's skills, Trade issues, etc.
Way Forward	Open question	Please describe your envisioned evolution of your innovation(s), milestones and goals, during project lifetime and 3 years after PLANET completion.
Project Reference	Open question	Please indicate the relevant PLANET deliverable(s) that document and relate to the innovation(s).
Project Impact Relevance	Open question	Please briefly describe the relation of the proposed innovation(s) to PLANET's impact points.
Innovation Level Self-Assessment:	Multiple choice question	Please select the type of innovation: - Incremental Innovation ²² - Breakthrough Innovation ²³ - Transformational Innovation ²⁴

²²Incremental Innovation: Small, yet meaningful improvements in your products, services or other ways in which you do business.

²³Breakthrough Innovation: This is a meaningful change in the way you do business that gives your consumers/clients something demonstrably new.

²⁴Transformational Innovation: This kind of innovation allows a company to fundamentally change how it does business, or it may introduce an entirely new marketplace to the company. For example, when Apple introduced iTunes, it suddenly and competitively began selling music and changed the music market.

4 Apply PLANET's Innovation Management

4.1 PLANET's Innovation Registry Items

PLANET's Innovation Registry questionnaire was circulated to PLANET consortium members twice during project lifetime at M14 and M26, capturing the innovative work of partners during project's whole lifetime. From PLANET's Innovation Registry Questionnaire circulations and the subsequent analysis of the responses 11 innovative services or ideas were collected, capturing consortium partners' innovative work or aspirations for their envisioned project's outputs. According to partners responses their innovations mainly are going to result in new services or improve existing processes of T&L actors across the various segments of the whole supply chain. Finally, Table 4 shows the 11 innovations identified along with the owner of each item, the name and the type of the innovation aims to address or result to, while each innovation is described in detail in the following paragraphs

Table 4 Innovation Registry Outline

Partner	Innovations Name	Innovation Type
IBM	Forecasting flows service for warehouses	New Improved Process and Organization Method
Hardt Global	Cargoloop	New Service
FV	Just-In-Time service	Significantly Improved Process, Consulting Service
NGS	Track&Trace Monitoring Service	Significantly Improved Service/Product
BlockLab	End-to-End Digital Document Management	New Improved Process
Konnecta	Smart contract interoperability ledger	New Service
eBOS	Physical Internet Software	Significantly Improved Product
CPSI	Seamless maritime and rail transport	Significantly Improved Process/Service
INLECOM	Collaborative Platform	New Organizational Method & Process
VLTN	PI Routing Algorithms	New Service
NEWO	New Logistics process method	New Organizational Method & Process

Furthermore, the information collected through PLANET’s Innovation Registry questionnaire where provided to PLANET’s ICB for early assessment and feedback, consisting of experts from various domains such as blockchain, ICT consulting or logistics services etc. . This step enabled us to achieve consensus and steer patent filling efforts towards project most promising innovation from an early point at project’s lifetime. In summary, the overall conclusions of PLANET’s ICB assessment of the innovations were that most of the items satisfying the utility criteria, as the spider graph below illustrates, meaning that they had a clear purpose and satisfying industries' needs or problem, while some outcomes seem to score lower in the novelty or non-obviousness dimension compared to other ideas. Finally, each PLANET’s Innovation Registry item is described in more detail below.

Figure 4 PLANET's Innovation Registry Innovation Assessment

IBM- Forecasting service for warehouses: A forecasting service for improving processes and organizational methods for warehouses. The flow forecasting service will predict the volume flows in a warehouse 24 hrs in advance to facilitate better planning of operations and resources for the next day. More specifically, this prediction can be used to optimize decisions regarding human resources allocation and transport vehicle that are required, since knowing the number of pellets meant to come into the warehouse, it can help make more precise decisions on the number of resources required for stocking and picking as well as the number of vehicles required to deliver these parcels. Furthermore, if there is available data on the final customer destination of pellets, this service has the potential to decide, in advance, optimal future routes resulting in reducing further operational costs and CO2 emissions. Finally, the forecasting service can be further advanced to make predictions

for longer periods in the future which can enable better long-term changes and optimisations to warehouse space, transport to and from warehouses and the resources employed within the warehouse.

The comments provided by PLANET'S ICB members regarding this service pointed out that for the successful implementation of it, its integration into the EGTN infrastructure is a key element and the central focus should be on the intended outcome, which is better planning, and not on its forecasting techniques. Furthermore, although forecasted volumes are critical for planning in warehouses, the forecasting window of 24 hrs may be too narrow, especially for warehouse planning in peak seasons/periods in which external factors such as the tight labor market, warehouse space constraints, and parcel carrier capacity play a significant role. Furthermore, another comment suggested that linking this innovation with customs procedures (dispatch of the cargo when it leaves the warehouse and notification to customs) would be an interesting path for exploring and an added value addition to the service. Finally, according to experts view although this service satisfied the patent's utility criterion and the same did not apply for being novel or non-obvious according to ICB views.

Figure 5 Forecasting flows service for warehouses ICB Assessment

Hardt Global (Cargoloop): is aiming to develop a new innovative solution for moving small and medium, standardized, and configurable shipment units - the Cargoloop. As the shipments of small and medium cargo units are an emerging challenge for the logistics market, which have not yet been fully addressed by the transport industry, the Cargoloop is envisaged as a complementary solution addressing this niche market and releasing operational stress on the existing cargo transport modes. The Cargoloop unique combination of features is addressed primarily towards a range of time-sensitive, demand-sensitive and high-value products, such as fresh food, horticultural products, pharmaceuticals, ecommerce, fashion, electronics, and high technology equipment. Cargoloop aims to bring benefits for other market segments, by creating opportunities for supply chain optimization and automation, increasing the coverage of existing logistics facilities, and reducing the need for capital investments in new or expanded facilities. The Cargoloop addresses the previously mentioned and future challenges of these industries by:

- Radically improving agility and efficiency of logistics operations for just-in-time and on-demand deliveries of small and medium sized shipments and packages, while minimizing their costs and carbon footprint

- Unlocking new market opportunities and economies of scale for time-sensitive and demand-sensitive products (reducing market access times, increasing geographical coverage, enabling new types of services and products)
- Enabling cost-effective transition to digital and automated logistics operations to increase responsiveness to demand volatility and changing customer requirements (logistics as a service, automated fulfilment, packaging modularization, physical internet)

Finally, within PLANET project HardGlobal aims to advance knowledge about the needs and challenges of the logistics sector and how future Cargoloop services can be shaped to address these needs. For example, the impact of Cargoloop on freight flows and the potential role of Cargoloop in Physical Internet implementation providing additional insights into the Cargoloop services needed in the future. Last but not least, the development of the test track is not directly related to the PLANET project, but the outcomes of the project will provide input for defining future tests and applications of the test track. Finally, PLANET ICB members highlight the importance and the need to align first and last-mile transport needs with Cargoloop's services for successfully carrying out this idea. In addition, although the novelty, utility, business benefits and potential market are clear, the main obstacle to this innovation in terms of exploitation and uptake is the high investment that it requires, as well as the relation to the project weak and likely not patentable.

Figure 6 Cargoloop ICB Assessment

FV Rail Shuttle: is developing a new service for improving container handling processes. More specifically, this innovative idea consists of an innovative “Just-In-Time” (JIT) rail shuttle service for container management. Although some PLANET’s ICB members view merits in this service including innovation and market potential, while other members raised concerns that this service may result in additional actions at unloading of the vessel and consequently, the time to unload a full vessel takes longer, resulting in longer time spent at the quay side, where the Terminal and ship-owner have no advantage. Therefore, this item did not reach consensus about its patentability prospect among the experts. Finally, another suggestion from one of PLANET’s ICB member was combining this service with for example autonomous shunting services for trucks would be an interesting path to be investigated and that can significantly and positively change the port management of containers and create even more efficiencies.

Figure 7 “Just-In-Time” (JIT) rail ICB Assessment

NGS (Track&Trace Monitoring Service): is developing a new product for which numerous services can be offered. More specifically, this includes a Smart Digital ID-card to the transported goods, providing a configurable device to the logistic units capable to implement specialised collection, monitoring and analytics functionalities to be provided real-time (if a connectivity is available) as well as stored in its internal memory (in case of lacks connectivity). Furthermore, the scalability of the measurements is guaranteed by the possibility of interaction of this device with other IoT nodes equipped with added value sensors, creating an ecosystem of integrations between the goods and sensors authorized to interact. Furthermore, these concepts can be also moved to implement an interactive and configurable device for the smart container, though it has to maintain the general-purpose characteristics of a container capable to encapsulate and accommodate the IoT connection of several and different goods. Finally, the service can offer numerous benefits to T&L actors, by improving the knowledge regarding the position and status of the goods along the supply chain and supporting decision making as well as it could provide new business models regarding the reuse of containers (e.g., pallets) and the asset management to improve their performance. PLANET’s ICB members’ pointed out that there are several solutions that are already being developed or available in the market as far as the prospect of this innovation is concerned. On the other hand, the market prospects of this solution are clear very and relevant to PLANET objectives.

Figure 8 Track&Trace Monitoring Service ICB Innovation Assessment

PoR/BlockLab Digital and Document Management: International shipment processes are captured in a stream of paper documents, in most cases in a paper of PDF format as well as these documents are obtained and distributed manually from and to each stakeholder (port/customs/transport/inspection) in shipment process. A

frequent problem that arises due to the manual handling of these documents are the loss of papers, manual errors causing delays and disputes, tampering with documents, and in general a lack of available real-time information for synchromodal dynamic management and optimisation. BlockLab is developing a platform for improving processes in the document management of transporting goods. More specifically, this platform will offer services that allow the creation of virtual shipments and enable end-to-end digitalisation and management of the documents related to each shipment. Document/data owners can authorise stakeholders for viewing, distribution and changing ownership for each document. For all these documents the platform provides cryptographically secured proof-of-integrity, proof-of-origin, proof-of-ownership, and proof-of-existence using the public Ethereum blockchain, while keeping commercially sensitive and GDPR data anonymous and secure. Key element of this solution the combination of the latest advances in machine learning and blockchain technology that allows for the trustworthy digitalisation and management of these commercially sensitive documents without a central party sitting on a pile of accessible highly valuable data. Finally, PLANET ICB members indicated that PoC should be implemented and tested under operational circumstances, as well as according to assessment this endeavor satisfied all patents criteria and is a very interesting and ambitious innovation for achieve end-to-end digitalisation and management of the documents related to each shipment.

Figure 9 Digital and Document Management ICB Assessment

Konnecta - Blockchain interoperability solution: The objective of the blockchain interoperability solution is to resolve technical issues that exist within the integration of various blockchain technologies that different actors use to support their respective business needs. The new distributed ledger technology service introduces two innovative outputs:

- The blockchain infrastructure that will interconnect existing blockchain systems and installations from existing T&L and SC actors.
- The prototypes of smart contracts facilitate, verify, or enforce a contract or an aspect of an SLA. Smart contracts can be triggered automatically when predetermined terms and conditions are met by encoding ‘if then’ rules that depend on other actions that occur in the supply chain and are recorded through the IoT and the connectivity infrastructure in the blockchain. Once the right conditions are satisfied, the smart contract also executes and records its outcome/transaction in the blockchain.

From the owner is a unique solution for interconnecting different blockchain systems which up until now has not been implemented in the T&L sector. Existing domain platforms gather all actors under a single blockchain umbrella which does not provide interoperability with other systems. Moreover, it is the first solution that offers a standardised technology for smart contracts to accommodate a wide range of T&L actors, together with their business and technical requirements. Finally, the extensive application of these solutions will facilitate the use of paperless transport documents, standardise and streamline interorganisational trade workflows by assisting towards cheaper, faster and more transparent communications and actions among different business players and/or business operations. Again, PLANET ICB members pointed out that operational testing/use of the solution is key and highlighted that this solution main aspect is the high potential for future exploitation and utility, although it was noted that other solutions using existing protocols and similar solutions have been piloted or are about to reach production (Tradetrust, Deliver/Naviporta) rendering it difficult to form a patent.

Figure 10 Blockchain interoperability solution ICB Assessment

EBOS (Software for PI Hubs):The PI concept and the adoption of the offerings of the EGTM infrastructure promises to realize open collaborations between PI Hubs (Distribution Centers DCs of today) by secure and trusted data sharing and moving physical goods around with shared resources, routing schedules, optimized procedures etc. The current ERP and WMS systems of companies are structured around the companies' own resources and plans, resulting the allocation of current resources, and planning of capacity remains within the company's domain and in isolation to any PI optimization offered. The proposed solution is a software module to be added to existing ERP & WMS systems which will do the following:

1. Communicate with external platforms for exchange of data and services through APIs (M2M and HMI interfaces)
2. Produce reports for the DC operational section to identify the new elements and ensure work capacity inclusion. Plans produced will include added resources and align execution with existing ones.
3. Update transactional ledgers in ERP to register transaction and values related
4. Indirectly savings will be produced by the reduction of vehicle runs, optimization of loading space, maximization of capacity scheduling and storage capacity exploitation.

Concluding, the proposed solution will offer integration with network resources and actors within the PI concept and eventually ability to incorporate details to existing infrastructure, enabling supply chain actors to rip the benefits of the concepts offered by Physical Internet and the notion of open collaborative networks with data

sharing. According to PLANET's ICB review of this innovation, the concept of this idea has clear relevance for the PI. But some experts point it out that such modules, as the one described being a middle ware solution that helps to integrate various systems, already exist in the market and therefore this innovation did not satisfied the non-obviousness criterion.

Figure 11 Software for PI Hubs ICB Assessment

CPSI – Integrating Transport Services: aims to develop solution and serviced for achieving seamless integration of maritime and rail transport by leveraging emergent technologies (particularly AI and blockchain) to improve multimodal transport planning and control as well as improve rail wagon design to carry reefer containers. The carriage of reefer containers, carrying high value cargo e.g., pharmaceuticals goods, by train is very much limited by the fact that rail wagons are not electrified. As a result, reefer containers are mostly carried by trucks that are equipped with reefer plugs. Some rail operators equip a few rail wagons with portable power packs, an inefficient and cumbersome solution. Therefore, there is a clear need to develop a more efficient and robust solution for powering the reefer containers. The solution's innovation lies in how the reefer containers are going to be powered. More specifically the solution under development aims to transform mechanical power, from the moving wheels and axles, into electric power and currently is at TRL level 2. Finally, this innovation offers a clear interesting solution for the reefer containers but some concerns were raised that the technology using movement of the wagon axles for electric power might be already there being an obvious solutions and it has a weak relevance to project scope.

Figure 12 Integrating Transport Services ICB Assessment

INLECOM – Collaborative Digital Platform: Operations in T&L are highly fragmented leading to inefficient use of resources and overlapping actions, resulting in increased operational costs and CO2 footprint for the different actors. Our concept aims to offer a digital ecosystem for designing and implementing “smart” and “green” operations in T&L. This concept aims to solve technical and business barriers by designing an agile platform aiming to accommodate all the different actors and their operations. The designed platform aims to enable collaboration and transparency in planning and executing operations of the different actors along the whole supply chain, from ports to last mile destinations. Therefore, it will facilitate the different actors to achieve increased efficiencies both in planning and executing their operations. To fulfil that mandate a database will be constructed for actors to interact through sharing data and critical information. The strongest aspect of this platform would be the optimization services that it will offer to users, built on the shared information/data provided, for simulating and predicting trade flows and key parameters for each actor's use case. Key aspect of this platform is it's innovative interdisciplinary modeling approach, utilising simulations for incorporating the effects of geo-economic and technological changes and the operational impact of aspects such as Synchronodal planning toward the PI, and the corresponding business models that supported by new generation optimization algorithms. Finally, PLANET ICB members concurred with the innovative dimension and ambitions of such platform, also pointing out that it aligns with PI principles and satisfying patents criteria.

Figure 13 Collaborative Digital Platform ICB Assessment

VLTN – PI Routing Service: is developing a new service for pairing the unique needs and preferences of each shipment/ consignee with the ideal carriers running the route. As the shipment is at the first node and at every other node that it reaches prior to reaching the destination, all route-service combinations for reaching the destination are collected recursively, and their performance is assessed considering transport services, transshipment and storage options in terms of all shipper criteria. These criteria can include routing options and available carriers including their capacity and performance, special carriage requirements, storage options and access to entire network as well as shipper/consignee carriage preferences in terms of cost, delivery windows, emissions etc . At each node all shipments are simultaneously assigned to route-service combos utilising a novel

pairing assignment algorithm to optimally match shipper weights. The novelty of this services is that it considers comprehensive shipment preferences that can potentially enable consignees to request and monitor multivariate performance indices and limits, as well as simultaneously optimises cargo to services, pairing for all shipments unique preferences by applying recursive multivariate assignment/ pairing problem. Finally, the main comment of PLANET ICB members raised the importance of operational testing/use of the solution during PLANET’s Living Lab operations while there was a consensus that his service satisfied the three patents criteria.

Figure 14 – PI Routing Service ICB Assessment

NEWO – New organisational process

The idea under investigation is to propose a new organisational method for taking transport traffic away from roads for modal shift. Current market practices are driving the opposite way with the B2C type of logistics, e.g. Amazon type logistics. The main goal of the idea under investigation is to achieve better results avoiding exponential parcel fragmentation and propose a new organisational method for Transport/logistics supply chain management by combining two key transport variables, that of Time and Capacity for producing positive effects and efficiencies. According to a survey of the transport and services gaps, the state of the art is penalized by a fragmented business environment particularly overland since o maritime the technical industrialization process has gone beyond the desired objective. PLANET ICB members pointed out that goals of this idea are highly ambitious and might benefit from clear delimitations of scope as well as various initiatives have tried to break through the siloed system and business environment. Finally, the innovation and technical dimension was not clear as well as another comment was that the exploitation potential needed further determination.

Figure 15 New organisational process ICB Assessment

Finally, several ideas of interest were documented through PLANET’s Innovation Registry and based on the evaluation of PLANET’s ICB some of them did not proceed in the patent filling process steps, as described in Table 2, on the ground that it was clear to the experts in the consortium a) if they can succeed to be granted as a patent, b) relevance to the core scope of the project, c) deemed to be obvious to one skilled in the art. For example, a class of ideas/outcomes such as that of NEWO or NGS’s did not move forward in the process as perceived from the experts of being relatively minor incremental steps or not having sufficient justification for achieving its scope and innovative ambition. Also, some other PLANET’s Innovation Registry items were discounted for another two main reasons a) for leading to patents of negligible value to the owner, b) that the inventive step not being sufficiently substantial and comply with the parameters around the test for novelty (which needs to be more than a mere/minor incremental improvement). Hence, considerable and valuable time/effort was saved protecting project resources and avoiding time-consuming processes. Concluding, 11 items were collectively discussed, assessed, and the project team chose that that BlockLab, VLTN and Inlecom items/ideas, that also satisfied all three patents’ criteria, to move forward with patent filling dockets preparations.

4.2 European Union Innovation and Intellectual Policy agenda

European Union transition towards the “knowledge-based economy” is a priority of the agenda of the Lisbon Summit (European Commission, 2003a) and the investment in education, research, and innovation are crucial elements to achieve these goals. According to EU Scoreboard 2021 report the overall innovation performance continued to increase in EU27 members countries in 2021 too, following a similar trend as the previous years with the main Summary Innovation Index²⁵ having a total improvement of 12.5% in innovation performance between 2014 and 2021, across all 27 Member States. On the other hand, Intellectual Assets index performance decreased -13% overall between 2014 and 2021 for the EU, due to lower performance in both patents and Design

²⁵ Summary Innovation index distinguishes between four main types of activities – Framework conditions, Investments, Innovation activities, and Impacts and has 12 innovation dimensions, capturing in total 32 indicators. For more information see Innovation Scoreboard 2021 <https://ec.europa.eu/research-and-innovation/en/statistics/performance-indicators/european-innovation-scoreboard/eis>

applications. A fact shared and stressed out to PLANET’s consortium during the project’s Innovation Management presentations, pointing out the importance of Innovation Management and patent filings benefits.

Figure 16 Summary Innovation and Intellectual assets Index for EU27 countries from 2014-2021²⁶

To continue with innovations and patents are an important element of EU updated industrial strategy for promoting Europe’s industrial transformation to a more sustainable, digital, resilient, and globally competitive economy. In achieving this goal of rendering Europe as a global innovation leader, Horizon2020 programs have a vital role in encouraging scientific excellence, promote new solutions and support to top researchers and innovators to drive the necessary changes for achieving this vision. In this context, according to the statistics illustrated at Figure 6, the EU has a performance lead over Brazil, China, India, Russia, and South Africa, and a performance gap with Australia, Canada, Japan, South Korea and the United States. More recently, between 2020 and 2021, the EU has closed part of its performance gap with Australia and Japan, but Canada, South Korea, while the United States managed to increase their performance lead both in terms of overall innovation and PCT patent applications.

Figure 17 PCT patent applications per billion GDP index for EU27 and selected global competitors 2014-2021²⁷

²⁶ European Commission, Directorate-General for Internal Market, Industry, Entrepreneurship and SMEs, *European innovation scoreboard 2021*, Publications Office of the European Union, 2021, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2873/725879>

²⁷ Source: [European and Regional Innovation Scoreboard 2021](#)

Another remark shared with consortium partners was that intellectual property assets (i.e. patents) are in the business core of many successful organisations and transactions related to technology. Licenses and assignments of intellectual property rights are common operations in the technology markets, as well as the use of these types of assets as loan security. Moreover, granted/issued patents also a) increase the book/asset value of companies holding the patent(s), b) increase confidence in investment contexts, c) provide exclusive rights, d) guarantee freedom of usage, exploitation, unimpeded by 3rd parties, e) raise the reputational and differentiation-with-competitor values to organizations. Furthermore, patents boost Europe’s reputation in innovation and scientific/research excellence on a global stage as well as can be cited and thus help improve h-index, i10-index and citation scores for researchers. Lastly, the Figure 7 summarizes a study conducted from IPMetrics²⁸ which was shared with the consortium in helping us understand the Commission’s IP impetus as discussed earlier. In addition, it helps us acknowledge and illustrate the commercial value underpinning the protection of European innovation as well as historical confidence levels on monetisation from a leading technology research and intelligence firm performing custom analysis on patent, scientific papers and market reports to drive business insights.

Concluding, all the aforementioned facts and diagrams have been brought to the attention of PLANET’s consortium members, enhancing their understanding and appreciation of the impetus from the European Commission for paying closer attention to commercially sensitive/strategic innovation in R&D projects.

Figure 18 Commercial Value of EU Patents

²⁸ <https://www.slideshare.net/IPmetrics/patent-values-in-the-evolving-ip-market-5587174>

4.3 Patent Filing Landscape and filings strategy

Patent office’s accept less *than 50%* of the candidate patents submitted to them according to WIPO statistics illustrated below. In order to overcome those high rejection rates and successfully patent PLANET's most innovative outputs, the consortium had to understand the underlying reasons for that phenomenon, which include inability to provide substantial evidence of novelty, concerns with obviousness and utility, and issues related to reduction to practice. In addition, of paramount importance was to take all the necessary steps to avoid those mistakes. Therefore, the KPI-based approach described in the previous section supports us in paying attention to these details and other essential variables for a successful parenting file application.

Figure 19 World Patent Activity²⁹

A key element at PLANET’s Innovation management was its patent filing strategy. In contrast to the USA where the patent filed at USPTO covers all US states making the filing at USA/USPTO straightforward (albeit interesting subtleties to pay attention to), the EU is much more complicated and fragmented. More specifically, in Europe each country is largely autonomous with different national requirements and patent agencies, rendering a

²⁹ Source: WIPO statistics database. Last updated: November 2021 <https://www3.wipo.int/ipstats/>

granted patent valid only in the country that issues the decision and on in the rest of the European countries. For example, a granted patent in Italy will not be valid in Spain or the UK (nationalization is a prerequisite) and even be rejected. Hence, in Europe, we have 3 options for filing:

- PCT (Patent Cooperation Treaty) – Universities have usually chosen this organization to file patents, it's reasonably speedy, however, it possibly does not represent good value, ROI nor practical use for Industry (or indeed Universities).
- EPO (European Patent Office) – a viable option, however the path has increased risks, success rates are low, rejection rates are high, and is perceptually difficult due to a higher bar/standard of patentability.
- WIPO Paris Convention and file first in France and USA on the same day

The characteristics of the aforementioned options are discussed in a little bit more detail below:

PCT is a request to defer the decision to file internationally by 30 months. It is not a patent application and never grants - thus, the PCT is not an asset like a patent application. Moreover, the PCT Request cannot be enforced like a patent granted from a patent application. Likewise, the cost of filing a PCT is dependent on the nature of the application, which is the subject of the PCT Request, and is generally payable to WIPO in Geneva and on or before the 30th month, the PCT needs to be nationalised (with associated costs). After attorney's fees, the PCT exercise represents a large cost for a document which never results in a granted patent. In addition, PCT Request is not classified as an asset on the balance of the owner, compared to a patent, and therefore it does increase the book value of the owning organization (Patent assignee). Bearing those facts in mind, the PCT Request is merely an "expense" and does not offer value to the commission/project, nor to the partners, nor to the European taxpayer.

Concerning the second option, EPO's is well known for its high standard of patentability. For example, if we are perceived to lack an "inventive step" in France then, unlike the EPO, a patent will grant in France on "novelty" so that the applicant has an enforceable right in Europe very quickly, whereas that same right would not exist under the PCT or the EPO. The costs for an EPO path are also so much greater (over double). Moreover, the EPO provides a single patent grant procedure, but not a single patent from the point of view of enforcement - hence the patents granted are not European Union patents or even Europe-wide patents, but a bundle of national patents (if nationalised). Thus, EPO implies higher cost, higher risk and statistically higher rejection rates. Therefore, PLANET leans toward local filings in a number of specific countries of interest – UK, France, Germany and Spain are typically the principal EU filing regions, instead of following the EPO path, to improve the filing efficiency and to reduce the related costs.

Finally, it should be noted that by leveraging WIPO Paris Convention and filing in the USA and France allows for a 9-month turnaround (Figure 10) by an examiner in INPI, which is the French version of USPTO, at lower standard of patentability (Novelty only). The results from France occur within 1-year period under the Paris Convention allowing us to abandon further investment if the result is not positive. This strategy allows to preliminarily adjust claims at the USPTO before examination based upon the results in France (i.e., to avoid unnecessary rejection in the US we can provide the France intelligence). Moreover, if we lack "inventive step" in France then, unlike EPO, patents will grant in France on novelty, applicants have an enforceable right in Europe quickly whereas that same right would not exist under PCT or EPO.

To conclude, following this method we are able to save legal expenditures, long-term cost, time, and resources by proactively adjusting our cases before patent office examination. More importantly, the Convention implies

each Contracting State must grant the same protection to nationals of other Contracting States that it grants to its own nationals. Consequently, the applicant may, within a given period of time, apply for patent protection in any of the Member States (12- month window) and these subsequent applications will be regarded as if they had been filed on the same day as the first application – i.e., they will have priority over applications filed by others during this interval and these subsequent applications and will not be affected by any event that takes place in the interval – e.g., such as the publication of an invention. Likewise, applicants seeking protection in several countries are not required to present all their applications at the same time but have 12 months to decide in which countries to protect them. Finally, from a strategic point of view and with a main interest to optimise the results with PLANET project lifetime, a unanimous agreement is to leverage the WIPO Paris Convention, and filing in Europe and USA on the same day (such that one application cannot be considered as prior art against the other), with the aspiration of evidencing successfully granted patents in the project’s timeline.

Figure 20 Timelines for different patenting options

4.4 Focusing on the Patentability and Market Aspect

An important aspect of technological change and R&D is the protection of new inventions or innovations. For this reason, intellectual property systems and rights (e.g. patents, trademarks etc.) play a crucial role in motivating and fostering innovation. In general, intellectual property rights are given by the government or any other relevant institution providing an inventor with the exclusive right to their invention. Also, Therefore, patent system safeguards that the innovator will reap the benefits of his work, since he/she preserves its exclusive exploitation from the owner and prevents others from copying or using it³⁰. In addition, from an academic and economic policy perspective, the majority economic growth and industrial organization literature³¹ also

³⁰ Competitive advantage refers to factors that allow a company to produce goods or services better or more cheaply than its rivals.

³¹ Aghion, Philippe & Howitt, Peter. (2009). The Economics of Growth.

emphasizes and empirically substantiates the importance of patent systems in providing incentives to firms for innovating, leading to new products/services as well as increasing product market competition (Scotchmer 2005³²). In turn, this product market competition fosters economic growth as it increases consumers' available options as well as forces firms to become more productive to survive and satisfy customer needs.

Furthermore, a patent is a lawful title that grants the owner the exclusive right to avoid others from making, utilizing, or offering for sale, selling, or importing a product that infringes their patent in countries for which the patent was given for a limited time (as much as 20 years). In return for this security, the owner must disclose the invention and diffuse the associated information and knowledge leading to creation of the invention to the public. In addition, while the systems give the owner the prerogative to his/her creation for a specific period, after the pre-defined period the invention enters the public domain and belongs to society. Therefore, even though a patent grants the "monopoly" right of the innovation to the owner, the details of new innovation are disseminated to the public which does not preclude other firms from undertaking similar endeavors or being inspired or improve them. To sum up, the main objectives of International/Jurisdictional Patent Systems are to a) Boost Invention: Property rights are protected to guarantee the creation and productivity and b) Promote Progress and "the general welfare" by disclosing innovations. This also helps, safeguarding new innovative companies or start-ups, so these can compete with already dominant business in the markets, serving the "healthy" competition among firms in the economy. In legal terms, PLANET innovations satisfy the legal definition of patentability if innovations are meeting one of the following a) a Process or Method, b) a Machine or Apparatus, c) an Article of Manufacture, d) a Composition of Matter (e.g., Chemical Compounds or Physical Mixtures), or d) an improvement of the latter.

Table 5 Patent types and examples

³² Menell, Peter S. and Scotchmer, Suzanne, Intellectual Property. HANDBOOK OF LAW AND ECONOMICS, A. Mitchell Polinsky and Steven Shavell, Forthcoming, UC Berkeley Public Law Research Paper No. 741724, Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=741424>

	What is Protected	Examples	Protection Lasts for:
Utility Patent	Inventions	iPod, chemical fertiliser, process of manipulating generic traits in mice	20 years from the date of filing regular patent application
Design Patent	Ornamental (non-functional) designs	Unique shape of a guitar, design for a lamp	14 years
Plant Patent	Newly discovered and asexually reproduced distinct and new variety of plant	Mutants, hybrids and newly found seedlings other than a plant found in an uncultivated state	20 years
Copyright	Books, photos, music, fine art, graphic images, videos, films, computer games	Michael Jackson's Thriller (music, artwork and video), Windows operating system	The life of the author plus 70 years
Trade Secret	Formulas, methods, devices or compilations of information which is confidential and gives a business an advantage	Coca-Cola formula, survey method used by a pollster, new invention for which patent application has not been filed	As long as information remains confidential and functions as a trade secret

4.5 Patent Requirements, Selection Criteria and Assessment

All PLANET's consortium participants were motivated to put forward compelling innovation propositions for patent protection, in an open as well as impartial competition, following the principles and criteria described in the previous chapters. In addition, PLANET innovation management organized specialized innovation deep-dive meetings, along with the appropriate checkpoints during the project's lifecycle, for bringing together the necessary technical, business, research and IP expertise and make them work together for distinguishing and deciding the innovations of the highest business, technical and research value for patent protection. In addition, project's IM apply some of the best practices from the WIPO Patent Drafting Manual can be used in terms of pertinent questions related to invention disclosure being put forward, in turn paying attention to some of the key questions asked therein (see Annex I). Also, PLANET IM leverage best practices and experience from actors within the consortium that have successfully surmounted the complex steps to yield successfully filed patents in recent years, in turn supporting the consortium in responsible recommendations, decisions and prioritization of PLANET's IM budget tasks. Focus areas for scoring and measurement of innovation are based on pre-established KPIs (Table 3) that collectively fall in to three categories of measurement:

- Alignment with EU and US patent law – which includes overcoming the tests for novelty thus ensuring that filed patents meet the patent office tests for uniqueness and extending the background art in new and non-obvious ways, in turn steering a path for filed patents to be successfully granted (at issuance stage) with approval from the respective patent offices. Ease of discoverability assessments will also be performed, taking the perspective that there is limited commercial use and value in filing strategic IP in situations where it not possible to reasonably demonstrate that a third party may have infringed at some future point down the road. Ease of avoidance will also be factored in to the KPI scoring, thus applying a weighting that measures the extent to which a third party could circumvent the inventive step(s) through an alternative or modified claim set or through implementing the inventive step in a different way and thus limiting the potential value and commercial significance of the invention.
- Commercial Value - of most significance is the application of an exploitation weighting to the inventions scored, to reduce the potential for innovation to “sit on the shelf” and not be exploited by the consortium's partners, thus incentivizing commitments to use and exploit the innovation commercially and, consequently, giving the commercializing actors a competitive advantage (as well as a valuable asset). Likewise, the background art and prior art landscape will be assessed, to understand the nature of the invention space, taking the view that well invented spaces have limited IP value potential and prioritizing IP budget in areas that will maximize the commercial value of patents granted at the patent office at issuance time. Other aspects such as IP revenue potential shall also be reflected in the scoring, allowing for the prioritisation of decisions where evidence of potential licencing, assignment and divesture values are deemed significant. Last, a final measurement in the scoring will pay attention to the innovation and its alignment with the projects broader commercial vision as expressed by the project's commercialisation plan.

As mentioned, identification, selection and prioritising of PLANET's inventions was a collaborative process, managed under confidentiality guidelines, open to all actors, and involving commercial, IP, research and business

experts from the consortium, guiding an organic free-flowing exchange of ideas and questions. The methodological framework (Table 6) allows these actors to have a naturally flowing conversation with the inventors while at the same time they keep the meeting focused on the goal of prioritising and discerning the more compelling innovations for patent protection, with discussions focused on: (1) supporting data to define the specific measure, dimension and grain of the score; (2) further questions relevant to substantiating score; (3) appropriate actions or decisions to be taken.

Regarding the scoring process, in order to calculate a KPI score along one or more dimensions, one needs to aggregate data from a multiplicity of sources. The goal is to ensure that we have captured all attributes that create a score for the stated values, and have the IDT validate the KPIs for each given dimension. When we use the term KPI metrics we are referring to a numerical measure that represents a piece of data in the relationship of one or more dimensions. An example would be: “importance to business and/or customers” from the perspective of market coverage. In this case, the measure would be euros (value) and the dimension would be territory (state). For a given measure, one may also wish to see the values across different hierarchies within a dimension. For instance, seeing value by city, region, or state would show the measured euros (value) by different hierarchies (cities, regions, and states) within the territory dimension. Making the association of a measure with a specific hierarchal level within a dimension refers to the overall grain of the metric. Looking at a measure across more than one dimension such as market value by territory (market coverage) and time is called multi-dimensional analysis.

Furthermore, PLANET's will use scores agreed in one or multi-dimensional analyses. More specifically, PLANET's KPIs represent a metric tied to a target with a stated KPI representing how far a metric is above or below of such pre-determined target. Scorecards in this context can be used to help align operational execution with innovation strategy with the goal of keeping the innovation focused on a common strategic plan. The primary measurement used will hence be scored KPI value indicators. These indicators will represent a composite of several metrics (shown in Table 3: Innovation Scoring KPIs) that measure the innovation ability against a strategic objective. An example of such a metric would be an indicator named “importance to customers/others” that combines quantitative/ weighted measure such as new customer acquisition with qualitative measure such as customer satisfaction with value proposition (quantitatively measurable with e.g. number of repeated products purchasing when applicable). By aligning KPIs and scoring with the PLANET business plan we are also able to help validate the importance of the score and separate the “must-have” from the “nice-to-have” inventions, thus prioritising commercial relevance.

Concluding, PLANET IM apply best practice in IP value creation to discern a small number of targeted patent assets, applying a spider diagram of KPI weighting as depicted in the figure below, aiming for high quality and high value patents. The methodology aims to see performance metrics that prioritise strong patents aligned with PLANET's project's goals with IP management guided as a knowledge management process involving many expert stakeholders that collectively comprise a common body of critical information and knowledge that is needed to discern the more strategic and commercially strategic innovation that aligns with the EC's brief, the objectives of the project and which incentivises the commercial ambitions of the project. This work will be done in close alignment with PLANET's commercialisation work items (Task 6.4), where the innovation management methodology and associated decisions will be guided by and informed by progress in T6.4 and, specifically, where T6.4 anticipates the more commercially relevant and commercially strategic innovation.

Figure 21 Patents scoring KPIs

Figure 6: Innovation Management Methodological Framework

5 PLANET Patent Filing Applications and Patents Descriptions

From day one of the project one of its high priorities was the protection of its strategic and/or commercial sensitive intellectual property via patents. For this purpose, the project's innovative ideas were identified, as presented in Chapter 4, and discussed with project partners, patent attorney and Inlecom experts in various R&D meetings. From the above-mentioned list, a set of 3 innovations were decided to move forward into the filling patent, as the remaining ones were rejected for various reasons. For example, having low chances of succeeding as a patent, not being very strongly connected to PLANET project objective, being obvious to one skilled in the art/industry, low commercial value or not satisfying the necessary novelty parameters. In this way, considerable and valuable time/effort was saved by speedily eliminating these early and quickly and without enacting time-consuming processes. The selected 3 patents have been filed in Greece, Belgium, and US patent offices, under the patent docket application numbers display in the table below (Table 5) as well as in the following sections the novelty studies for each invention along with their respective workflow and process they implement are presented. Lastly, it should be noted that the complete documentation for each patent amounts to circa 100 pages and it is not included in the current report due to its length. But it is available upon request if needed by the European Commission and/or the EC reviewers in audit and/or for any other reason for each patent.

Table 6 Patents Applications Dockets

Patent Application Docket Name	Patent Application Docket Number
6200-037BE Multimodal Real-Time Decentralized Supply Chain Coordination	2022/5298
6200-038BE Dynamic Routing Optimization	2022/5509
6200-038GR Dynamic Routing Optimization	20220100363.00
6200-038U Dynamic Routing Optimization	17/735,379
6200-039BE Infrastructure Planning Responsive to Simulated Network Changes	2022/5517
6200-039GR Infrastructure Planning Responsive to Simulated Network Changes	20220100362.00
6200-039U Infrastructure Planning Responsive to Simulated Network Changes	17/735,398
6200-037BE Multimodal Real-Time Decentralized Supply Chain Coordination	2022/5298

5.1 Patent 1 : Digitalization and decentralization of multi-modal logistics documentation

The first patent (620-037BE) was filled out on behalf of BlockLab which is involved in PLANET's Living Lab 2, having a thematic focus on synchromodal dynamic management of TEN-T & intercontinental flows for promoting rail transport.

Background of the invention

The logistics supply chain initiates from the shipment of goods from a seller, the receipt in delivery of the shipment by a purchaser and the other parties are involved with the transport of the goods from the seller to the purchaser. The documentation generated during these movements, from the seller to purchaser, includes at least a purchase order from the seller, an invoice from the seller to the purchaser, a carriage contract for the shipment of the goods by each party to the transport of the goods, or in the alternative, a bill of lading. Finally, it should be pointed out that in most instances the transport of goods involves multiple different modes of transport including multiple trucks complemented by sea, rail or air segments. In such a case of multi-modal transport, the amount of documentation can become unwieldy.

In addition, for dynamic optimization at every logistic hub, the cargo/shipment-related documents must be updated, according to the optimized routing/transport digitally travel along with the physical shipment, meaning that governmental organizations such as customs agencies along the route need to be authorized to view certain documents. Consequently, it is desirable to digitize the documentation and to store the documentation in a central location so that all parties to the transport of the shipment of goods from seller to purchaser can assess the nature and state of movement of the shipment of goods.

To do so, however, requires each actor in the multi-modal supply chain to confirm its documentation to a specific structure and to conform its use of the computer software managing the documentation to a specific range of applications. Furthermore, another important problem is the assurance the supply chain actors need as to the integrity of the documentation, and nothing prevents tampering with the content of the documentation once stored as well as concerns related to vulnerabilities to cybersecurity attacks and reduces its resilience

Description of the Invention and the Process

The present invention embodies a programmatically executable process. The foregoing flowchart and block diagram illustrated the architecture, functionality, and operation of possible implementations of systems, methods, and computing devices according to various embodiments of the invention. In summary, upon the receipt of the documents from a user participating in the platform, the platform generates a hash of the corresponding one of the documents, signs the hash with a cryptographic key of the user, stores the corresponding one of the documents in connection with a shipment implicated by the document and the user, and submits the hash to a blockchain interface with a directive to write a ledger entry in the blockchain in correspondence to the shipment and user. Throughout, the platform maintains publication of a query interface enabling receipt of a query from one of the users participating in the platform as to a status of the shipment and a response to the query by retrieving ledger entries from the blockchain interface in respect to the shipment and reporting the retrieved ledger entries to the querying one of the users.

Scoring of the patent and relationship to the project and partner background

Blocklab is focusing on the two largest challenges of T&L sector a) the energy transition and b) the transformation of global supply chains towards 100% digital. The core business activity of Blocklab is the development and testing of innovative applications based on emerging technologies such as Blockchain, AI, IoT and Machine Learning and turn them into sustainable ventures. Currently, Blocklab has a portfolio of solutions, including Distro, a joint venture with Standard & Poor for peer-to-peer energy trading, QuayConnect, a collaboration with British Telecom for fully automated customs clearance into the United Kingdom and Naviporta, a Blockchain Infrastructure as a Service. Furthermore, the medium-term business goal is to develop or advance company's expertise in digital twins, decentralized data management, incentivization of data sharing and algorithms that make decentralized networks more efficient, which filled patent based on.

The patent achieved a broad consensus from the experts board and scored 8.9/10 scoring and yielding the scores on our A+B+C axes, as shown in the spider graph below. This score was achieved as the invention aligns with project and EC objectives as it can eventually speed up and streamline freight flow as well as enable the provision of a rich real-time information flow that is very useful for a PI. It has clear innovative dimension as it combines the latest advances in machine learning and blockchain technology that allows for trustworthy digitalization and management. Finally, the patent benefits Blocklab in several ways by:

1. strengthening the reputation as innovator and as an emerging technology thought leader, not only with our clients and stakeholders but also in the war for talent
2. builds on previous work we have done in other projects and as such extends our company's know-how and portfolio of existing solutions
3. provides potential investors in our ventures with protection of the solution that's being developed
4. provides evidence of the uniqueness of our solution to clients, stakeholders and investors
5. it is in line with BlockLab short term strategic goals of advancement of knowledge and capabilities as well as exploiting the invention within PLANET and after project timeline.

Figure 22 KPI Scoring Patent 1

Novelty Study Search Results

- i. [US 2009/089145](#) | **G06Q Freight Transport Logistics Performance Modeling Software System And Process**

A freight logistics efficiency modeling software embodied in a system and a process for implementing the software. The software interface allows an interactive, visual, user-defined freight transport supply model to be created at the instructions of the user. The model includes a seaport node, hinterland nodes, transportation links that represent transport pathways between nodes, and transportation transition nodes to represent discrete alterations of transport performance along transport pathways. The present invention allows a user to model logistics chain from a low level of abstraction, and to create highly effective theoretical alterations of existing models to examine proposed changes to an existing logistics chain. The use of existing standards allows completion of a model lacking complete data values, and further allows comparison of existing logistics chains to benchmark logistic chain performance and normal logistic chain performance.

- ii. [US 10,600,021](#) | **G06Q SYSTEMS AND METHODS FOR OPTIMIZING DELIVERY ROUTES USING FLEET VEHICLES AND THIRD-PARTY DELIVERERS**

Systems and methods including one or more processing modules and one or more non-transitory storage modules storing computing instructions configured to run on the one or more processing modules and perform acts of receiving website orders on a website of an online retailer for delivery of products, determining at least one fleet delivery route for delivery of the products using a vehicle fleet of the online retailer, and performing a randomized node movement on the at least one fleet delivery route to optimize delivery of the products. Performing the randomized node movement can include selecting a source route, selecting a first node from the source route, selecting a destination route from the at least one fleet delivery route and one or more third-party delivery routes, evaluating a cost differential of inserting the first node into a third-party delivery route, and inserting the first node into first third-party delivery route.

- iii. [WO 2019/116053](#) | **G01C System Arranged To Calculate A Route In A Fixed Transport Network, And Related Personal Computing Device, Methods And Computer Program Products**

There is disclosed a system including a computer, a server and a personal computing device, the personal computing device including a screen, a processor and an application, the personal computing device operable to communicate with the server, the computer configured to process transportation network data, the transportation network data including: (i) a plurality of transportation network stops, each transportation network stop including an identifier and location data, and (ii) a plurality of transportation services, each transportation service including a service identifier and a respective plurality of transportation network stops, each respective plurality of transportation network stops comprising a subset of the plurality of transportation network stops; wherein the computer is configured to organize the transportation network data into a plurality of scalar dimensions, each scalar dimension including an upper distance bound and a lower distance bound, wherein the computer is further configured to store the transportation network data that has been organized into the plurality of scalar dimensions; the server operable to transmit to the personal computing device at least a subset of the stored transportation network data that has been organized into the plurality of scalar dimensions; the personal computing device configured to receive and to store the at least a subset of the stored transportation network data that has been organized into the plurality of scalar dimensions; the application executable on the processor of the personal computing device to receive user input of a start and a destination,

and to calculate a route from the start to the destination using the stored at least a subset of the stored transportation network data that has been organized into the plurality of scalar dimensions, and to display on the screen data relating to the calculated route.

iv. [WO 2015/067799](#) | **G01C Navigation System For Taking Use Restrictions Into Consideration In Particular, And Method For Operating Same**

The invention relates to a navigation system with a database (1), a route calculating device (2), and a user interface (3). The aim of the invention is to find paths to special destinations using such a system while taking into consideration use restrictions. This is achieved in a first step in that a number of one or more special destinations (14, 15, 16, 17, 19, 20) is linked to a respective plurality of connection nodes (8, 9, 10) while assigning a first total path, which connects the respective special destination to the connection node. For each of a number of ascertained special destinations (14, 15, 16, 17, 19, 20), the user interface (3) indicates the total path length of the first total path to a connection node (8, 9, 10) linked to the special destination, in particular the closest connection node (8, 9, 10) linked to the special destination, and for the special destinations for which the first total path has use restrictions, the user interface marks the special destination with additional specifications.

v. [WO 2021/097104](#) | **G01C Improved Logistical Management System**

Disclosed herein are system, method, and computer program product for a transporting of a good. An embodiment operates by receiving a user request for the transporting of the good from a pickup location to a destination location. Thereafter, a corresponding pickup, first intermediate, a second intermediate, and destination node are identified on a pre-generated graph, and transportation edges each relating to a transit cost associated with one of the pickup, first intermediate, second intermediate, and destination locations. Subsequently, a subgraph of the pre-generated graph comprising the pickup, first intermediate, second intermediate, and destination node, as well as the transportation edges, are generated. Based on the subgraph, Based on subgraph, a preferred route from the pickup location to the destination location having a lowest transit cost for transporting the good is generated.

5.2 Patent 2 : Recursive multi-criteria PI freight orchestration process

The second patent (6200-038U) was filled out on behalf of VLTN which is involved in PLANET's Living Lab 1 focusing on Intelligent decisions at transport and logistics hubs, including operations and routing. In the subsequent paragraphs the novelty study, along with invention details are outlined.

Background of the invention

Supply chain management includes various actors such as suppliers, manufacturers, logistics and transportation companies and retailers that deliver component parts and/or finished products from one source to the end customer. Efficient supply chain management is crucial as optimized operations can result in lower costs as well as a faster production cycle. A key aspect of this process is the effective routing of a shipping container, from the origin to a destination. Typically, the freight forwarder selects a route for transporting shipping freight according to the shortest geographic path to the destination in order to cause the delivery of the shipping container by the requested delivery date and minimizing the number of modes of transport utilized in shipment for avoiding a more complex oversight burden.

Furthermore, in supply chain logistics, the Physical Internet or "PI" is defined as an open global logistics system founded on physical, digital, and operational interconnectivity, through encapsulation, interfaces and protocols. Furthermore, PI concept aims to lead to improvements in distribution and logistics by applying some of the principles of the digital Internet to the physical movement of goods. To that end, the Physical Internet is centered around the basic notion that a shipping container, as a package encapsulator, behaving like packets of the well-known Internet Protocol (IP) of the digital Internet, and moves from an origin to a destination along a route according to transport directives akin to the transport control protocol (TCP) of the digital Internet.

The preference by the freight forwarder to limit modes of transport in order to minimize the management burden of the transport of freight as well as the notion of PI remain absent in the decision-making of the freight forwarder. In addition, as the freight is determined statically prior to the initial movement of the freight from its origin and the routing decision-making is limited to simplistic criteria such as basic cost of transport, specific container criteria such as temperature control and size, the knowledge of potential transporters in an existing relationship with the freight forwarder etc. . In addition, other more complex constraining criteria such as emissions goals, safety and past performance are ignored or cannot be taken into consideration. Finally, since complex constraints and simplistic constraints are valued differently by different customers, it can be challenging to formulate a selection process satisfactory to each of the different customers.

Description of the Invention

The invention provides for recursive multi-criteria PI freight orchestration. a set of possible routings may be computed between a geographic origin and geographic destination of freight based upon a data model of freight transport nodes within a geographic region. Then, for each routing a route value is computed, recursively from the start node to the end node with numeric values produced beginning at the end node and unwinding to the start node. Additionally, numeric values are weighted to prioritize some of the values over others. The values are then combined to produce a route value for each of the possible routings and a specific one of the routings is selected for the transport of the freight based upon the preferred route value. As the freight traverses the selected routing, the process repeats substituting a contemporaneous node for the start node. In this way, the desirability of a particular routing can be determined recursively at each node along the transport path from geographic origin to geographic destination with multiple criteria considered by weighted differently according to value.

Scoring of the patent and relationship to the project and partner's background

VLTN is a Belgian SME, dedicated to data-driven consulting, optimization and research & development on Green supply chain and logistics. VLTN vision is to achieve net-zero GHG emissions supply chains that 'evolve' and adapt to an ever changing environment, delivering balanced value to both business and societal actors. This can be achieved by utilizing advance analytics, dynamic optimization methods, and logistics innovation management to look into the future and anticipate changes in the highly complex supply chain and logistics industry, offering viable alternatives for efficient and sustainable operation. In the project, VLTN uses graphs and supply chain modelling to interconnect different transport networks and to achieve interoperability of transport flows between them as well as define interorganizational workflows that support business process interoperability across transport networks, where the patent filled focuses on. According to expert's view this patent scored 8.6/10 in aggregate for satisfying the patentability criteria (novelty, utility and non-obviousness) as well as the patent builds on VLTNs expertise to deliver optimized supply chain operations based on the principles of the Physical Internet, promotes PI concept and the adoption PI driven solutions. More specific, the patent

operationalizes the principles of the PI, diverging from the existing operational principles of scheduling vehicles based on demand to navigating cargoes (such as containers) with high efficiency based on recursive routing decisions on fixed operational schedules. Finally, VLTN envisages the exploitation and development of software based DSS solutions to assist supply chain stakeholders operational and tactical decision through establishing new innovative services linking its established Supply Chain Knowledge Graph technology with collaborative multi criteria DSS for transport and for Intelligent PI Nodes and PI Network services.

Figure 23 Patent 2 KPI scoring

Novelty Study Search Results

Related Art

- i. [US 2008/308470](#) | G06Q **Logistics System For Transporting Postal Items And Method For Determining A Transport Path**

There is provided a logistics and method a logistics system for transporting a mailpiece along a transportation route within a postal distribution network, the transportation route comprising several nodes of the postal distribution network. An exemplary logistics system comprises a node that corresponds to a delivery point, the node being associated with a first unambiguous identifier and a node that corresponds to a sorting point, the second node being associated with a second unambiguous identifier. The exemplary logistics system further comprises a node that corresponds to a subsequent node in the transportation route being associated with a third unambiguous identifier, the node that corresponds to the subsequent node in the transportation route being associated with another node that either precedes or follows the subsequent node in the transportation route.

- ii. [EP 1,145,090](#) | G06Q **DYNAMIC TRAFFIC BASED ROUTING ALGORITHM**

A method and system are disclosed for dynamically routing a material transport vehicle (MTV) using traffic based parameters. A controller (502) directed to allocate a material transport vehicle (MTV) to a particular node (104),

selects the material transport vehicle that is physically closest to the particular node (104). The controller (502) calculates an optimal route by identifying the possible routes between the initial node (102) of the material transport vehicle and the destination (120), and analyzing each of the nodes (102 through 120) according to a metric function by calculating a metric function value for each identified route. The controller (502) then selects the route for the material transport vehicle (MTV) having the smallest metric function value. The metric function may include parameters associated with each of the nodes in the material transport system including a node-to-node distance parameter, a node crossing parameter, and the number of MTVs in a queue at each node within the route. In one embodiment, the metric function is given by a mathematical formula.

iii. [US 6,285,951](#) | G06Q **DYNAMIC TRAFFIC BASED ROUTING ALGORITHM**

A method and system is disclosed for dynamically routing a material transport vehicle using traffic based parameters. A controller directed to allocate a material transport vehicle to a particular node, selects the material transport vehicle that is physically closest to the particular node. The controller calculates an optimal route by identifying the possible routes between the initial node of the material transport vehicle and the destination node, and analyzing each of the nodes within each identified route according to a metric function by calculating a metric function value for each identified route. The controller then selects the route for the material transport vehicle having the smallest metric function value. The metric function may include parameters associated with each of the nodes in the material transport system including a node-to-node distance parameter, a node crossing parameter, and the number of material transport vehicles in a queue at each node within the route.

iv. [US 2009/089145](#) | G06Q **Freight Transport Logistics Performance Modeling Software System And Process**

A freight logistics efficiency modeling software embodied in a system and a process for implementing the software. The software interface allows an interactive, visual, user-defined freight transport supply model to be created at the instructions of the user. The model includes a seaport node, hinterland nodes, transportation links that represent transport pathways between nodes, and transportation transition nodes to represent discrete alterations of transport performance along transport pathways. The present invention allows a user to model logistics chain from a low level of abstraction, and to create highly effective theoretical alterations of existing models to examine proposed changes to an existing logistics chain. The use of existing standards allows completion of a model lacking complete data values, and further allows comparison of existing logistics chains to benchmark logistic chain performance and normal logistic chain performance.

v. [EP 2,757,504](#) | G01C **ROUTE PLANNING**

A computer-implemented route planning method comprises determining source and destination nodes in a graph data structure based on a route planning query, executing an initial graph search on the graph data structure using graph costs based on real-time traffic data, wherein the initial graph search starts at the source node and settles nodes until it stops, and computing one or more routes to the destination node from one or more of said settled nodes using precomputed data based on traffic prediction data, thereby to determine a route from the source node to the destination node via one of said settled nodes.

vi. [US9,175,972](#) | G01C **ROUTE PLANNING**

A computer-implemented route planning method comprises determining source and destination nodes in a graph data structure based on a route planning query, executing an initial graph search on the graph data structure using graph costs based on real-time traffic data, wherein the initial graph search starts at the source node and settles nodes until it stops, and computing one or more routes to the destination node from one or more of said settled nodes using precomputed data based on traffic prediction data, thereby to determine a route from the source node to the destination node via one of said settled nodes.

vii. [WO 3,025,507](#) | G01C **FOUR-DIMENSIONAL ROUTE PLANNER**

A route planner (110) uses a recursive algorithm to determine a lateral path, and an adaptive algorithm to determine a vertical path. The vertical path is adjusted based on hazard areas (120, Figs. 2, 3a and 3b) represented by horizontal polygons (Fig. 3a) having top and bottom altitudes. The route planner (110) attempts to find a route which meets a required time of arrival window. A route may be broken into multiple starting and ending points, with desired arrival times specified for each ending point.

5.3 Patent 3: Physical internet dynamic principal interface node (PIN) port selection

The third patent (6200-039U) was filled out on behalf of Inlecom Group and around the notion of the EGTM platform and on the notion of enabling collaborative and data driven T&L. More specifically, the invention is a method for physical internet (PI) port selection.

Background of the invention

The Physical Internet³³ or "PI" is an open global logistics system founded on physical, digital, and operational interconnectivity, through encapsulation, interfaces and protocols. To that end, the Physical Internet centers around the basic notion that a shipping container, as a package encapsulator, behaves like packets of the well-known Internet Protocol (IP) of the digital Internet, and moves from an origin to a destination along a route according to transport directives akin to the transport control protocol (TCP) of the digital Internet.

Furthermore, the PI models the entirety of the logistics supply chain from source to sink inclusive of sea, air, road and rail. As noted in Patrick B.M. Fahim et al., On the Evolution of Maritime Ports Towards the Physical Internet (Futures 134, August 27, 2021), the maritime port forms an important component of the holistic logistics supply chain linking sea transport to overland transport. Thus, a bottleneck can occur at the maritime port where the transition of freight from ship to shore can be slowed owing to several factors including the processing of necessary papers relating to the freight, the speed at which the freight can be physically offloaded from ship to shore and then subsequently placed on road or rail transport, and of course the throughput available on the roadway and railway corridors leading from the maritime port into the hinterland.

Consequently, managing the movement of freight from ship to shore through a maritime port requires substantial advance planning. Indeed, it is often the case that many different maritime ports are able to process freight en route to the same destination and that a specific one of those ports is selected on the basis of optimal cost, optimal throughput or ecologically minimal impact. In PI, a maritime port is classified as a principal interface node or "PIN" referencing the primary interface between sea and land and a set of maritime ports through which

³³ Professor Benoit Montreuil, a professor in the department of operations and decision systems at the Universite Laval in Quebec and a member of the College-Industry Council on Material Handling Education (CICMHE) conceived of PI as an improvement to distribution and logistics by applying some of the principles of the digital Internet to the physical movement of goods.

freight can be forwarded to a common destination is referred to as a PIN cluster. Optimally routing freight in the PI from sea to land requires the a priori selection of a PIN from a PIN cluster according to the criteria established for the corresponding PI model. Once selected, the PI model presumes that the freight will be received at the maritime port of the selected PIN.

In reality though, it is highly likely that a ship will not be able to reach a designated maritime port. Several factors influence the possibility that a ship carrying freight and destined for a designated port may be required to divert to a different port. Primary examples include weather and traffic, but other possibilities include labor shortages at the designated port, or mechanical failures of offloading equipment at the port. In any instance, optimization of the PI model will be disrupted. As such in the event of a port disruption, a decision must be made somewhat quickly depending upon the distance of the ship from the designated port. Yet, the decision making, expedited as it may be, is rife with consequence, and selecting an alternative maritime port within the cluster can result in a failure to meet the time and cost constraints of the shipment of the freight, as well as impart an unacceptable ecological cost in terms of a higher level of emissions.

Description of the Invention and the Process

The invention describes a Physical Internet (PI) dynamic principal interface node (PIN) port selection includes selecting a primary maritime port as a PIN in a routing of freight aboard a sea going vessel from an origin node to a destination node in a PI model and receiving a disruption event in the PI model indicating an inability of the vessel to berth at the primary maritime port. A cluster of alternative PINs is determined in connection with the destination node of the PI model and a routing score computed for each alternative PIN based upon a cost of routing the freight through each alternative PIN. Finally, a new routing is established in the PI model utilizing an optimal alternative PIN in lieu of the selected PIN based upon a corresponding routing score, and a message is transmitted to the vessel to divert to a secondary maritime port associated with the optimal alternative PIN.

Scoring of the patent and relationship to the project

Inlecom is a European SME focusing on research and development of collaborative platforms and technologies. Inlecom research and commercial aspirations focuses on the fact that actors across Europe need a secure and trusted vehicle to share data and information for effective collaboration, especially in supply chain markets, as well as optimize business processes where this patent builds on. Furthermore, in these efforts Inlecom has already achieved a patent-protected commercially sensitive innovation behind concepts of a shared intelligence "data space" that is configured to address the needs of a logistics community. According to expert's patent review, this patent scored 8.7/10 in aggregate with the most important aspect of it being its innovative modeling approach. Furthermore, it addresses project and EC goals as it's vision is to become a tool for successfully realizing the concept of Physical Internet in T&L as well as utilize innovative technological concepts for flows and operations planning and management. Finally, the patent is aligned with INLECOM strategic vision to support T&L actors, for cooperating in order to improve existing business operations and become more efficient and competitive, protect Inlecom work and expertise in the domain of T&L as well as solidify company's reputation as an outstanding innovative solution provider to the industry.

Figure 24 Patent 3 KPI scoring

Novelty Study Search Results

i. [US 10,936,992](#) | G06Q **LOGISTICAL MANAGEMENT SYSTEM**

Disclosed herein are system, method, and computer program product for a transporting of a good. An embodiment operates by receiving a user request for the transporting of the good from a pickup location to a destination location. Thereafter, a corresponding pickup, first intermediate, a second intermediate, and destination node are identified on a pre-generated graph, and transportation edges each relating to a transit cost associated with one of the pickup, first intermediate, second intermediate, and destination locations. Subsequently, a subgraph of the pre-generated graph comprising the pickup, first intermediate, second intermediate, and destination node, as well as the transportation edges, are generated. Based on the subgraph, a preferred route from the pickup location to the destination location having a lowest transit cost for transporting the good is generated.

ii. [US 2021/348926](#) | G01C **An Apparatus For Determining An Optimal Route Of A Maritime Ship**

An apparatus for determining an optimal route of a maritime ship comprises a database configured to store a service speed of the maritime ship. The apparatus further comprises a processor configured to generate a plurality of state nodes, to determine a plurality of time sets, to append the plurality of time sets to the plurality of state nodes to obtain a plurality of appended state nodes, to generate a plurality of edges based on the plurality of appended state nodes, to generate a graph based on the plurality of appended state nodes and the plurality of edges, to apply a preliminarily generated optimal route algorithm on the graph to obtain a preliminarily defined route path, and to apply a genetic algorithm based on the preliminarily defined route path to obtain the optimal route of the maritime ship.

iii. [WO 2018/149901](#) G01C **Route Planning Of A Vessel**

It is an object to provide route planning of a vessel. In an embodiment, an apparatus is disclosed. The apparatus comprises: a processor; and a storage comprising a set of instructions that, when executed by the processor,

cause the apparatus to: receive first data regarding reliability of a first wireless connection; receive second data regarding cost characteristics of a first wireless connection; receive third data regarding reliability of a second wireless connection; receive fourth data regarding cost characteristics of a second wireless connection; receive a route plan of a vessel configured to navigate and control the vessel, wherein the first and the second wireless connections are used to control the route plan and navigate the vessel; and modify the route plan based on the first, second, third and fourth data so as to process the reliability and cost characteristics of the wireless connections for the route plan. The route of the vessel may be optimized and balanced with respect to safety of the connections and cost of the connections. Other embodiments relate to a ship or a shore operator having the apparatus, and a method and a computer program for performing the operations of the apparatus.

- iv. Non-Patent Literature Patrick B.M. Fahim et al., **On the Evolution of Maritime Ports towards the Physical Internet, in Futures 134, 1023834 (27 August 2021)**

The Physical Internet (PI) is a novel, comprehensive and long-term vision of the future global freight transport and logistics (FTL) system, which is aimed at radically improving its efficiency and sustainability. As research on the PI concept is still young, the functioning of maritime ports in the context of the PI is still underexplored. Our aim is to contribute to the scientific debate about radically different futures for maritime ports around the world, by identifying their possible future development paths towards the PI. We construct an evolutionary port development framework that identifies the main dimensions of the PI in relation to ports, including governance, operational, and digital aspects. To design the future development paths towards the PI, we conducted a scenario analysis and used a Delphi survey amongst port development and PI experts. The resulting expectation is that a fully globally functioning of the PI may not be reached by 2040.

6 Conclusions

The current report presented PLANET's Innovation Management timeline and activities that were designed and implemented for achieving the filling of three innovative and commercially valuable patents at European and US patent offices.

In more detail, PLANET's Innovation Management approach was influenced by several innovation tools, methods, and frameworks such as S-curve, Oslo Manual, Stage-Gate model, Funnel model, Monniers' innovation matrix, Innovation Radar and CENT 16555-01 (technical specification report). Furthermore, the first step was to identify project's key outputs and capture all the necessary information needed for evaluating and prioritizing the three most innovative and strategically important outcomes for patent filings. For this reason, a tailor-made questionnaire, based on the aforementioned Innovation Management methodologies was created, and circulated among consortium partners. This resulted to PLANET's Innovation Registry and the identification of 11 innovative ideas or project's outcomes aiming to improve or introduce new innovative services to T&L logistics actors, enable collaboration among various actors and/or optimize their business operations.

Subsequently, the Innovation Management goal was to prioritize and protect PLANET's most innovative and strategically important outcomes through patent filings. In close collaboration with the relevant consortium partners this resulted in the preparation and filling of patent's docket's about three inventions for multimodal real-time documentation coordination, dynamic routing optimization and a collaborative process for PI port selection.

In more detail PLANET's first patent focuses on the digital management of multi-modal logistics documentation using blockchain technology. This invention has potential benefits for the broader industry as it can help minimizing labor required for handling and verifying shipments' documents across the various stakeholders, resulting in important savings as well as eliminate dispute expenses for the industry. In addition, using blockchain technology for decentralizing the digital document handling contributes to increased security, protection and transmission of critical logistical supply chain documents. Finally, this end-to-end digitalization of shipments documents enables the streamline freight flow as well as to produce rich real-time information flow about the shipments that is very useful for PI implementation principles.

The PLANET second filled patent applies a new method of recursive algorithm to route services with the aim to reduce operational costs of T&L actors. The novel pairing assignment algorithms aim to assist freight forwarders to optimize their operations in terms of satisfying multiple KPIs and requirements, while considering much more complex routing options. This is achieved by decomposing supply chain operational complexity in a number of criteria e.g., load factors, distance, cost, pollution etc., where the algorithms seeks optimal routes recursively and optimises considering multimodal option.

The third patent focuses on dynamic principal port (PIN) selection for a vessel affected by disruptive event indicating an inability of the sea going vessel to berth at the primary maritime port. In more detail and according to a set of criteria established in the corresponding PI model, a new routing is established in the PI model utilizing an optimal based upon routing score, and a message is transmitted to the vessel to divert to a secondary maritime port associated with the optimal alternative PIN. The goal of this process is to enhance the responsiveness of the relevant infrastructures to cargo flows changes, and thus reduce costs and time associated with the operations, planning and the management of cargo flows.

Concluding, the three filled patents except for protecting and promoting project's vision and objectives for smart and green T&L and significantly under the PI paradigm, they also aim to be an asset to the patent owners, enabling the further development or exploitation the outputs of unimpeded by competitors, enhancing their innovation credibility and improving their market position trough. Finally, it is also worth noting that PLANET's patents support and align with inventors strategic and business vision for providing new service to T&L stakeholders for optimizing resources, reducing costs and environmental footprint of the T&L industry, resulting from increased transparency, accountability and collaboration among the various actors.

Annex I: Invention Disclosure Forms

Simplified Invention Disclosure Form

Name: _____

Organisation: _____

1. Summary of INVENTION

2. Broadly speaking, what do you believe is likely to be new/novel here

3. What, specifically, do you believe is uniquely new/novel (it is good to be as specific as you can here)

4. Please share/comment on any background and/or related art

5. Rationale– please say a few words as to why you would like to file a patent (e.g. reputational value for your organisation, protecting commercially sensitive/strategic innovation that you hope to commercialise etc)

6. Other points/feedback you would like to add, if any

7 Preparing for a Patent Adjudication Session - Inventor Guidance

Preparing for a Patent Adjudication meeting

Broad guidance to inventors:

- Prepare a slide deck to summarise your invention clearly and concisely, use as many slides as needed **but** make sure to respect the time limit allowed for both presenting and Q&A
- In the slides to make sure to cover :
 1. the “what is truly new/ novel” (i.e. the inventive step you believe is patentable) - *this is part is really key and where Inlecom and the Patent Attorney will be paying the most attention*
 2. the relevance of your invention to the project (one slide sufficient)
 3. **Good to have** -> a flowchart to describe how your invention would actually work one-level-down/under the hood (one to two slides sufficient)
 4. the relevance of your invention to you and/or your organisation – e.g. reputation value, business value, competitive advantage, commercial interest, etc (one slide plenty explaining a clear benefit of some kind)
 5. Optionally – one slide at the end to share why you feel your idea should be prioritised for a formal patent filing